

GENDER, POLITICS AND THEIR EFFECTS ON SOCIO-SOCIETAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The Female folk have over the years lagged behind in politics, notwithstanding their numerical strength. The world's conferences of women in Mexico in 1975; Copenhagen in 1980, Nairobi in 1985, and Beijing in 1995, organized by the United Nations have no maximal effects or impacts on the total number of women's involvement/representation in decision making the world over. This study is an examination of the effects of female's misrepresentation/under-representation in politics on the socio- societal development of the Country, with focus on Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. Related literatures were reviewed and liberal feminist theory was used as the theoretical framework. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design and the purposive sampling technique. Data were collected from 260 respondents through the use of questionnaire and determined via the Taro Yamane, while the simple percentage was used as a method of data analysis. Findings from the study revealed that, poor representation/ involvement of the women folk in politics has negative effects on the socio-economic or socio-cultural development of the society. The study recommends that, concrete policies/laws should be enacted and adopted for female's proper involvement/representation in politics and decision making. Stereotyping cultural norms should be abolished and women should be sponsored to get involved in politics.

Keywords: Gender, Politics, Effects, Socio-societal Development and Akwa Ibom State civil service.

Introduction

For decades now, politics and feminine participation/involvement has been the focus of so many scholars/authors, especially the feminists. Researchers of gender and politics study/analyze women's political participation in the context of their patriarchal/socio-cultural norms vis-à-vis its effects on societal development. Though the formal norms that impede/hinder the feminine political representation have faded away, informal rules/norms and more importantly, some socio-cultural

practices still serve as barriers to women's participation/representation in politics even with the official announcement of women's inclusion in politics in 1995, as captured in Beijing declaration. Gender norms and archaic cultural practices undermine feminine's roles in public, and this promotes the resistance against women's political leadership and aspirations. This stereotyping norms that keep women out of politics also shape how people vote/elect and how women spend their time and behave, generating practical constraints to their participation in public and political life.

Women's ability to vote and be voted for (franchise), engage in politics as returning officers, representatives; voters, campaign sponsors, and community mobilizers have long ago (and still now) been shaped by gender norms in various ways. For instance, the prevailing norms about women's family responsibilities, the belief that women should always be voiceless in politics or be passively represented deny them their basic voting rights world wide for centuries, and in turn affects the rate of development in the society.

Although women are discouraged from voting in some contexts (as men and women in most democracies tend to vote at about the same rate), there is a change attributed to gender equality in education and even in career progression. Be that as it may, it could be observed that the role of women has gradually shifted/changed from the passive tagged housewife status/designation of performing complementary roles like care-giving, to more supplementary roles, ranging from being business entrepreneurs, policy makers, bank managers to political leaders or appointees. That notwithstanding, women still lag behind in global political engagement - joining political parties, funding political campaigns, influencing in choosing other appointees, because all these have also been moderated and shaped by prevailing cultural norms.

Women, all over the world encounter greater hurdles/hindrances in political participation. Men are always over-represented in leadership positions, even though women's mobilization/ equal re-presentation and quota are always proclaimed and advocated for, they have been less successful in pushing for party support to address the structural inequalities. In this regard, participation of the males and females in politics and decision making differ amongst countries, though basically, in favour of the male folk. Women are under-represented not only politically but economically and in decision making; they are seen as the minors and sometimes their votes do not count (notwithstanding their numerical strength) as they must toe the line of the ruling party whether they like it or not. It is an undeniable fact that, Nigerian women have been marginalized, excluded, and relegated as far as politics and decision making are concerned. They play the second fiddle, not authorized to explore their

full/rich God-endowed potentials, and as such, development and progress have been undermined. Both the society and Government itself have been gender biased.

However, shifting the intellectual battle ground from a focus on the isolation of women to a focus on gender seems to stimulate a more panoptic understanding of the cooperation and conflict between women and men as Wach and Deeves (2000) have noted. There are few women in political and leadership positions in Nigeria. The question now is; why are women so poorly represented in leadership positions? This and other questions would be analyzed on the course of this research.

Aside from cultural norms and patriarchal arrangements, there are several reasons why the women folk are under-represented in politics and decision making. Below are some of the factors that count for under-representation of women in politics:

- * Lack of Government Intervention.
- * Violence on female political aspirants.
- * Poor level of female education.
- * Lower level of female employment.
- * Archaic cultural norms and practices.
- * Lack of effective laws/policies for the incorporation of females in politics.
- * Low levels of female income.
- * Stigma against women that involve in politics.
- * Lack of confidence in the women folk.
- * Women's unwillingness to be involved in politics.
- * Access to good information.

Statement of Problem

Practically, the involvement of women in decision making and politics has so far received a relatively low attention even when there have been a public declaration that women should be given and accorded (40%) reasonable quota in political participation and decision making. In as much as women the world over are the primary caretakers for the young ones, even to the adult dependants, they play significant roles in facilitating or inhibiting changes in both families and the society at large. Gender stereotypes have hindered women's political involvement and representation and have thus hindered women's political candidature. This also affects voter's decision of electing women for certain political functions.

Indisputably, political parties are male dominated, with 85.8% men in leading positions. Discriminatory/violent practices are still rampant between males and females. In political participation, women are fronted to contest, but at the end, stands a very minimal opportunity of winning; parties do not implement supportive

measures (like funding political campaigns) for female political aspirants. They are often allowed limited access to funds, training, mentoring and God-fatherism as far as politics is concerned. Sex-typing has really affected the world's notion about political involvement/participation. In a nutshell, gender determines who can vote, who is elected, who runs the office, who commands authority, who takes decision, and who is more vulnerable to discrimination and sexual harassment in politics.

However, efforts to increase feminine political involvement and representation have not yielded the desired result; women are not still fully engrossed or incorporated in political leadership. Recently, National Assembly rejected bills that were meant to involve women in political activities in Nigeria and there was a protest by various women's groups including wives of State Governors condemning the National Assembly.

Objective of the Study

The study sets out to examine whether or not poor/under-representation of women in politics affects socio-societal development. It has the following as its objectives:

- * To examine factors that impede political representation of women in politics.
- * To examine whether or not party system affects women's political involvement/participation.
- * To identify factors that facilitates female political representation.
- * To find out societal support/encouragement women would love to get to enhance greater participation.

Research Questions

- * Does poor representation of women in politics influence socio-societal development?
- * What are the factors that impede female political representation?
- * In what ways can party system affect female political involvement?
- * What strategies could be adopted to enhance female political inclusion?

Significance of Study

This study recapitulates the influence of poor feminine political participation on societal development. The study will make greater contribution to gender research by determining the influence of non-inclusion of reasonable number of women in politics on the societal development. This will educate the women by providing knowledge/strategies that can help enhance their involvement in politics. Policy makers can also use findings derived from this research to address gender imbalance in politics and decision making, while it also serves as another opportunity to test the liberal feminist theory and to see its relevance in today's society.

Review of Literature

As part of the inclusion project, Feminist scholars have advocated for greater women's political representation. Most researchers' findings and recommendations are of the view that party and electoral quotas should increase the numbers of women in legislatures (Dahlerup 2006; Krook, 2009). Lovenduski (1981), Randal (1982), and Lovenduski and Norris (1995) examined women and politics in a more traditional sense. Their works x-rayed electoral institutions, political parties and political behaviours, showing where women fit and what their impact is.

Men make better political leaders than women (Setzler, 2019), an extreme misguided and stereotypic belief created to deprive females' active participation or involvement in politics and decision-making. Predicated on a survey conducted in 2018, most participants inadvertently demonstrated their biasness towards female political leaders without understanding society's impact on their perception (Setzler 2019). The level of female participation in Nigerian Politics is very low compared to their male counterparts. The Nigerian government has been very reluctant in implementing laws to improve gender equality in politics, despite formal support for it. The progress is uneven and indisputably slow.

Though progress has certainly been achieved with regards to women political participation over the last 20 years, the proportion across the globe has increased from 13 percent (13%) in 2000, to 25 percent (25%) in 2020; some regions have experienced greater gains, such as Africa, where the number of women legislators increased from 11 to 24 percent. The theme for international women's day 2001, "Think equal, build smart, innovate for change", was chosen to identify innovative ways to advance gender equality and the empowerment of women while accelerating the 2013 Agenda, building momentum for the effective implementation of the new U.N Sustainable Development Goals. With all these, women still play the second fiddle in politics as Gjermeni (2021) says, even though progress has been made over the years, and women are present in parliament; still, the political sphere remains quite socially homogenous. Kakuru (2001) added that apart from deep-seated stereotypes, believing in the ineffective leadership of women emerges from the fact that women lack the economic base which would enhance their political participation.

Violence during election and violence against women candidates is a barrier that can not be overemphasized. Valerie Bryson (1999) in her research sees women as an oppressed group who had to struggle for their own liberation against oppressors — that is, against men. This radical feminist is of the stand that the exploitation of women is carried out by men and that primarily, it is men who have benefited from the subordination of women. A number of radical feminists believe that rape and

male violence towards women are the methods through which men have secured and maintained their power, thus, for instance, Andrea Dworkin (1981) saw pornography as encouraging men to possess and control women, while Robin Morgan (1980) declared that pornography is the theory, rape is a practice (cited in Bradly, 2007). In the same vein, Susan Brownmiller (1981) believed that rape was a method used to control women.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted for this study is the liberal feminist theory also known as mainstream feminism. This is the main branch of feminism that focuses on achieving gender equality through political and legal reforms within the framework of liberal democracy as informed by human right perspectives. Theorists of liberal feminist include *Mary Astell (1666-1731)*, *Mary Wolstonecraft (1759-1799)*, *Harriet Taylor (1807-1858)*, *Johnstuart Mill (1806-1873)*, *Elizabeth Cady Stanton (1815-1902)*, and *Virginia Woolf (1882-1941)*.

Liberal feminist theory of the eighteenth, nineteenth, and early twentieth centuries focus on women's ability and right to participate in public life and exercise their rights. This group places great emphasis on the public world; especially laws, political institutions, education and working life, and considers the denial of equal legal and political rights as the main obstacles to equality. Notably, liberal feminism is largely an offshoot of social liberalism and includes both social liberal and social democratic streams, as well as many often-diverging school of thoughts, such as equality feminism, equity feminism, care ethical liberal feminism, conservative liberal feminism, difference feminism and liberal socialist feminism. Liberal feminism is closely associated with liberal internationalism.

Liberal feminism believes women are being relegated and denied of their rights and as such, liberal feminism has worked to bring women into political mainstream to get involved in politics and decision making. Historically, liberal feminism was called "bourgeois feminism", and was mainly contrasted with the working-class "proletariat" women's movements, which eventually developed into what was called socialist and Marxist feminism.

Liberalism stresses freedom of women and equity of opportunities; and views sex segregation in respect to social, political, economic, and religious provisions in the labour market as ways of depriving women of their rights and emphasizes the rights of an individual woman, and aims at granting access to equal rights and representations through legislation.

The liberal feminist theory is considered relevant to this study because it emphasizes gender equality, without disputing the facts that, there exist some biological differences between men and women. They do not see these biological differences as justifications for inequalities between sexes - not having equal social and political rights, not earning equal pay for the same job, not gaining equal political opportunity and engaging in decision making. Therefore, this theory tries to emphasize equal rights and liberties for the women folk while down playing the dominance nature of men in the society.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted because it allows a small group to be used to describe and analyse an entire population. The purposive sampling technique was used to purposely select more women as study participants. The study population were staff of Akwa Ibom State civil service, which according to 2022 annual report, has a total population of **17,625** (Seventeen Thousand, Six Hundred and Twenty-Five), and the Taro Yamare was used to determine the sample size from which a total sample size of 260 (Two Hundred and Sixty) was selected. Data was collected using structured questionnaires and analysed using simple percentages (%).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Information of Respondents

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
<u>SEX</u>		
MALE	80	31%
FEMALE	180	69%
TOTAL	260	100%
<u>AGE</u>		
20-30	80	31%
31-40	60	23%
41-50	100	38%
51-60	20	8%
TOTAL	260	100%
<u>MARITAL STATUS</u>		
MARRIED	230	88%
DIVORCED	10	4%
WIDOW	10	4%
SEPERATED	10	4%
TOTAL	260	100%

**EDUCATIONAL
QUALIFICATIONS**

F.S.L.C.	10	4%
O.N.D.	50	19%
H.N.D.	100	38%
B.S.C.	80	31%
M.S.C.	15	6%
P.H.D.	5	2%
TOTAL	260	100%

YEARS OF SERVICE

10-19	100	38%
20-29	100	38%
30 years and above	60	24%
TOTAL	260	100%

Table 2: Response on the Extent to which Women are Given Equal Opportunities to Participate in Politics and Decision Making

VARIABLES	YES(%)	NO(%)
1 women are allowed equal opportunity in politics and decision making	90(35%)	170(65%)
2 The female quota in politics have increased drastically since the Beijing conference	80(31%)	180(69%)
3 Women earn same wages with their male counterparts	70(27%)	190(73%)
4 Women are given free hands to make decision in politics	90(35%)	170(65%)
5 FIELD WORK 2022		

Table 2 shows that majority of **170(65%)** of the respondents disagreed with the assertion that women are given equal opportunity to participate in politics and decision making, while 90 agreed, that is, 35% of the respondents agreed to the fact that women are given equal opportunity to participate in politics and in decision making. In the same vein, a majority which was **180 (69%)** disagreed with the assertion that female quota in politics has increased drastically since the *Beijing Conference* while 80(31%) agreed to it.

However, 190(73%) respondents disagreed that women earn the same wages with their male counterparts, while 70(27%) agreed to that. This means that majority affirms that women do not earn the same income as their male counterparts.

170(65%) respondents disagreed that women are given free hands to make decisions in politics, while only 70 agreed. This means that majority of 65% disagreed that women are given free hands to make decision in politics.

Table 3: Responses on the Extent to Which Socio-Cultural Norms\Practices Influence Women's Involvement in Politics

	YES(%)	NO(%)
1 Do people still believe the archaic sayings that women's place ends in the kitchen	160(62%)	100(38%)
2 Do majority of the citizens have confidence in the leadership capabilities of the female	80(31%)	180(69%)
3 Do women themselves believe they can succeed and support each other	70(27%)	190(73%)
4 Most of the women see others who participate in politics as being way word	190(73%)	70(27%)

Table 3 shows that 160 (62%) respondents agreed that people still believe in the archaic saying that, women's place end in the kitchen, while only 100 (38%) disagreed, showing that people still maintain this archaic position.

However, 180 (69%) respondents disagreed to the fact that majority of the citizens do not have confidence in the leadership capabilities of the females, while 80 (31%) agreed to it, meaning citizens do not have confidence in leadership capabilities of women. On the other hand, 190 respondents, being 73% disagreed to the assertion that women themselves believe that they can succeed and they will actually support one another; while only 70 (27%) agreed to it. This means that majority of the respondents believed that, women themselves do not support or believe in each other or their leadership. Nevertheless, 190 (73%) also agreed to the fact that most women see others who participates in politics as being wayward, while only 70 (27%) disagreed with this.

Findings

The study reveals that archaic cultural norms or practices have adverse effects on female participation in politics. The analysed data showed that 62% (160) of the respondents were of the view that, Women's place ends in the kitchen, while only 38% disagreed with the assertion. It has also revealed that 65% (170) respondents believe women are not given free hands to make decisions in politics; and this corresponds with the findings of the inclusion project Squires (1999), which aims at exposing the absence of women in politics, leading to partial, shallow and biased knowledge and to integrate women into the theories, institutions and practices from which they had been excluded.

It goes on to reveal that women are not given free hands to make decisions in politics, as only 35% of that 90 respondents responded affirmatively when they were asked if women are given free hands to make decisions in politics. On the other hand, 170 respondents, which is 65% said no to the assertion.

In the same vein, 65% of the respondents said no, when they were asked if women are allowed equal opportunities in politics and decision making, while only 35% said yes. This finding corresponds with the literature of Gjermani (2021), which states that even though progress has been made over the years, and women are present in parliament, still the political sphere remains quite socially homogenous.

Furthermore, 73% responded negatively to the question whether women themselves believe they can succeed and support each other, while only 27% responded affirmatively. This finding corresponds with the literature of Setzler (1919) in which men are seen to make better political leaders than women.

However, 180 or 69% responded negatively when they were interviewed if majority have confidence in the leadership capabilities of the females, while only 31% (80) responded positively. Also, 190 respondents responded that most of the women see others who participate in politics as being wayward, while only smaller proportion of 27% saw it otherwise. This is in tandem with the survey conducted in 2018. Most participants demonstrated their bias towards female political leaders without understanding the society's impact on their perception (setzler 2019).

Conclusion

The study findings have affirmed to the fact that low women participation in politics has been influenced by the ancient cultural norms or practices which aver that women should not be allowed to display their God-given potentials in politics but their powers should end in the kitchen. However, lower levels of female employment, income and education have also affected women's involvement in politics. Lack of government's implementation of effective laws and policies that back up women and guarantee their total rights have also hindered the women folk from political participation.

It is notable that there is violence in elections, especially against women; sexist or societal attitudes based on traditional or religious fanatics, who see women that involve in politics as being wayward, and corrupt political system are some of the hurdles on the path of women's involvement in politics and decision making.

Recommendation

Given the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The cultural beliefs or practices of seeing women fit for expressive role and not instrumental should be abolished.
2. Financial support should be provided for female politicians to boost their participation.
3. Awareness and sensitization programmes should be conducted to encourage and emphasize the importance of women's participation in politics and decision making.
4. Laws against violence on female politicians should be enacted.
5. Employment opportunities should be provided for women to boost their income level.

References

- Acher, J and Freeman, S (1989). Gender Stereotypes of academic disciplines. *British Journal Educational Psychology*, 39, 306-313.
- Acker J. (1990). Hierarchies, jobs, bodies: A Theory of gendered organisations: *Gender and society* 4(2): 139-158.
- Ajayi, T. (2019). Women and Nigerian's 2019 Elections Retrieved May 22, 2019 from kujenga Amani Website. <https://kujenga-Amani.Src.org/2019/02/15/women-and-Nigerians-2019-elections/>
- Andrea, D. (1981). *pornography: Men possessing women*; Putman United States ISBN: 978-0-399-12612-2.
- Asubiario-Dada W. & Gaynor, C. (2017). Thinking and working politically for legal reform on gender equality. *Voices for change legacy Paper*, (July) 1-2.
- Bottero, W. (1998). Clinging to the Wreckage? *Gender and legacy of class sociology* 32(3): 469-490.
- Bourdieu, P. (1984). *Distinction: A social critique of the judgments of taste*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Brownmiller, S. (1981). *Against our will; Men, Women and Rape*, Brooklyn, New York.
- C A (online, 1999). *complete marquis; who's who 1995*. Oxford Companion to women's writing in United States 1995.

- Cheeseman, N., Cooper-knock, s. J, & Elder, (2016). Calculating Gender Representation in Nigeria, Lagos.
- Chinoy, E. (1967). Society: An introduction to sociology. New york; Random house
- Cottais, C. (2020). Liberal feminism gender geopolitics institute retrieved 2022, August 16 from: <https://1gg-geo.org/wp/content/uploads/2021/08/199-ccotais/liberalfeminism2020p.d.f>.
- Dahlerup, D. (2006). Women, quotas and politics, 1st Edition. London Routledge
<https://doi.org/10.4324/97802030>.
- Delvin C. & Elgie R. (2008). The effects of increased women's Representation in parliament: The case of Rwanda. *Parliamentary Affairs*. 61 (2), 237-254.
- Donner, W (1993). John Stuart Mills liberal feminism. *Philosophical studies: an international journal for philosophy in the Analytic Tradition*, 69 (213), 155-160
- Edward, R. Sphino, M. D. (1994). The practice of group Analysis. *Journal of American psycho-analytic Association, New York City*, volume 42, issue 3.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0003065194042003330>
- Friednan, B (1963). The feminine mystiques. WW Norton & Company.
<http://doi.org/10.093/p9/gsn007>.
- Jollie Bako, M. S., Syed, J (2018). Women marginalization in Nigeria and the way forward. *Human Resource development international*, 21(5), 425-443
<https://1wk.nd.org/1080/13618868.2018.1458567> hoy. P.C, et al. (eds.), women's voices 1990.
- Lovenduski, J and Norris, P. (1995). Recruitment: Gender, Race and class in the British parliament. Cambridge University press.
- Mill, J.S (2006). The collected works of John Stuart Mill
- NCWD (2016). Who are those making key decisions; A survey of women in politics
- Randal, V. (1982). Women and politics, 1st Edition Red. Gobe Press London,
<https://doi.org/101007/978-1-349-16880-4>.

- Squires, J. (1999). *Gender in political theory*. Baltimore: Paul H Brookes Publishing & co.
- Taylor, M. (1994). Gender and power in counseling. *British Journal of Guidance and Counseling*, 22(3) 319-326.
- Thibaut, L., Magne, M. & Setzler, B. (2019). Imperfect competition, compensating differentials and Rent Sharing in the US Labour Market, 2019 meeting papers, 1583, society for Economic Dynamics.
- UNIFEM and UNIC (1995). Beijing declaration and platform for Action: Fourth World conference on Women held in China. Lagos, UNIFEM.
- United Nations (1995). Beijing declaration and platform for Action, critical; area G, "women, power and decision making".
- Valerie, B. (1999). *Feminist debates: issues of theory and political practise*. Macmillan Education, Uk. ISBN: 033361392, 978033613399
- Whitehead J. M. (1996). Sex stereotypes, gender identity and subject choice at A-level Educational Research, 38(2) 147-160
- Zerilli, L. M. (2006). Book review: Wettgenstein: A feminist interpretation. *Saga Journals*, volume 34, issue 2 <https://dio.org/10.1177/0090591705279608>.